

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of pyridopyrazole and pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]dihydrothiazole

M. B. Deshmukh*, S. A. Deshmukh, S. S. Jagtap, A. W. Suryavanshi, S. D. Jadhav and P. V. Anbhule

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : m_deshmukhl@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : 6-Methyl-1,3-dihydro-4*H*,7*H*-pyrazolo[2,3-*c*]pyridine-4-one (4) were synthesized by microwave as well as conventional method. The reaction time reduced 10 times than that of conventional method. The pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]dihydrothiazole (8) were synthesized by reacting phenylisothiocyanate with 1-carbethoxy-5-amino-pyrazol-4-ene-3-one and were screened for their antimicrobial activities.

Keywords : Microwave assisted synthesis, pyrazolo[2,3-*c*]pyridine-4-one, pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]dihydrothiazole, anti-microbial activity, amino pyrazole.

Introduction

Pyridine ring annulated with pyrazole ring i.e. pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines are important in organic synthesis due to their interesting biological and pharmacological properties¹ such as vasodilators, hypoglycemic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic and anti-pyretic, ACTH (Adenocorticotropic hormone) releasing factor, CRF (Corticotrophin releasing factor) antagonist activity. Moreover, other pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines have been proved to be active against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria², as cholesterol forming-inhibiting compounds³.

Results and discussion

Considering the enhancement in the reaction rates and formation of the cleaner reaction products, in present section, we have reported the synthesis of pyrido[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivatives by Conrad-Limpach reaction by both conventional and microwave irradiation. The cyanoacetohydrazide on intramolecular cyclization afforded 3-amino-pyrazol-2-ene-5-one (2). This compound (2) on treatment with ethylacetoacetate gave the corresponding *N*-(pyrazol-2-ene-5-one-3-yl)-3-oxobutanamide (3) which was subsequently cyclized to the corresponding pyrido[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivatives (4). The formation of compounds (3) and (4) by

microwave irradiation indicated that the reaction time reduced 10 times than that of conventional method (Scheme 1).

By considering the various applications of amino esters of pyrazole, we tried to synthesize amino ester of pyrazole by the reaction of ethylcyanoacetate and hydrazino ethylcarboxylate. Same compounds on further treatment with phenylisothiocyanate afforded thiourea derivative which was converted to the targetted substituted thiazinopyrazole (8).

Isothiocyanates are distinguished as the useful intermediates for the preparation of thioureas, thiosemicarbazides etc. Hence, our attention was attracted to transform the amino group of the compound (6) in to thiourea derivative (7). Hence, to achieve this isothiocyanate was used to obtain the thiourea derivatives from 1-carbethoxy-5-amino-pyrazol-4-ene-3-one (6). IR spectrum of 1-carbethoxy-5-amino-pyrazol-4-ene-3-one (6) confirmed the presence of ester and amino group at 1753, 3246 cm⁻¹ respectively. ¹H NMR spectrum displayed a triplet and a quartet at δ 1.27 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 4.19 ppm (2H, q, CH₂CH₃) respectively. The broad singlet observed at δ 6.5 ppm was assigned for NH₂ group.

The chemical behavior of the amino ester towards isothiocyanate was investigated. Thus, treating amino

ester with isothiocyanate, in the presence of EtOH/KOH gave thiourea derivatives of amino ester (7). IR spectrum of it displayed an absorption band at 3116–3215 and another band at 1750 cm^{-1} assigned to NH and C=O of ester group. ^1H NMR spectrum showed a triplet at δ 1.1 ppm due to CH_3 , a quartet at δ 4.2 ppm due to OCH_2 , a multiplet between δ 6.9–7.6 ppm and two broad singlets at δ 4.6, 7.1 and a singlet at δ 10.1 ppm assigned aromatic protons and CONH protons, respectively.

Table 1. Yields and reaction time used for the microwave assisted synthesis

Compd.	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Microwave method		Classical method	
		Reaction time (min)	Yield (%)	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)
3	>270	4	78	10	65
4	>300	4	72	10	60

Antibacterial activity :

The biological activities of these compounds have been evaluated by using agar diffusion medium. All the compounds (3, 4, 7 and 8) (250 ppm) were screened for their antibacterial activities against the *S. aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*-2510 using standard antibiotic drug *Streptomycin* sulphate as a control and dimethyl formamide as a control of the solvent. Plates were incubated for 48 h at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the zones of inhibition were measured in mm and results have been incorporated in Table 2. All synthesized compounds were found to be moderately active against both types of bacteria.

Antifungal activity :

Similarly, the compounds were also tested for their fungicidal activities against *Aspergillus niger*-MTCC 2255 and *Penicillium chrysogenum*-NCIM 723 using Greseofulvin as a control. The careful scrutiny of the results revealed that the series of *N*-(pyrazol-2-ene-5-

one-3-yl)-3-oxo-butanamide (3), 6-methyl-1,3-dihydro-4*H*,7*H*-pyrazolo[2,3-*c*]pyridine-4-one (4), thiourea derivatives of 1-carbethoxy-5-amino-pyrazol-4-ene-3-one (7), pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]dihydrothiazole (8) exhibited the spectacular anti-fungal activities against test organism *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*.

The melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded using KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum one FTIR spectrometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO on a Jeol-JMSD-300 spectrophotometer. Microwave irradiations were conducted in a domestic microwave oven [SAMSUNG M197DN (2450 MHz, 1500 W)].

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of compounds (zone of inhibition in mm)

Compd.	Bacteria		Fungi	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>
3	–	18	28	26
4	6	28	28	34
7	6	15	31	24
8	–	23	32	24
<i>Streptomycin sulphate</i>	15	34	–	–
Flucanazole	–	–	30	30
DMF	–	–	–	–

Cyanoacetohydrazide (1a) : To a freshly distilled ethyl cyanoacetate (0.136 g, 1 mmol), hydrazine hydrate (0.048 g, 1 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 h. The colourless crystals obtained were filtered and washed with pet ether. Yield 90%; m.p. 105 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3403–3348 (NHNH₂), 2260 (CN), 1703 (CO), 1621, 1528 cm⁻¹.

Phenylcyanoacetohydrazide (1b) : To a freshly distilled ethylcyanoacetate (0.079 g, 1 mmol), phenyl hydrazine (0.136 g, 1 mmol) was added and further refluxed in 5 ml CHCl₃ for 6 h. The solvents were removed under reduced pressure to get solid residue and crystallized from ethanol. Yield 75%; m.p. 120 °C;

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 3.6 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.9 (1H, bs, NH), 6.9–7.8 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.0 (1H, s, NH) ppm.

3-Amino-pyrazol-2-ene-5-one (2) : Cyanoacetohydrazide 1a (0.500 g, 1 mmol) in 5 ml MeOH and KOH (0.100 g) was refluxed on an oil bath for 2 h, cooled and solid separated was filtered, recrystallized from DMF to get coloured needles. Yield 95%; m.p. 197 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3000–3330 (NHNH₂), 1689 (C=O), 1653 (C=N), 1610, 1469 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.0 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.2 (2H, s, NH₂), 9.5 (1H, s, NH) ppm (Found : C, 36.3; H, 5.0; N, 42.4. C₃H₅N₃O required : C, 36.2; H, 5.1; N, 42.3%).

***N*-(Pyrazol-2-ene-5-one-3-yl)-3-oxobutanamide (3)** :

Conventional method : 3-Amino-pyrazol-2-ene-5-one 2 (0.270 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.130 g, 1 mmol) was refluxed in 5 ml DMF for 10 h in oil bath, cooled. The solid separated was filtered and washed with DMF.

Microwave method : 3-Amino-pyrazol-2-ene-5-one 2 (0.270 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.130 g, 1 mmol) in 5 ml DMF was taken in a conical flask and irradiated in a domestic microwave oven for the period of 4 min with intervals of 30 s with intermittent stirring. After cooling the reaction mixture product separated as a yellow solid, which was filtered and washed with DMF. IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3152, 3086 (NH), 1675 (C=O of pyrazolone), 1616 (C=N), 1542 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.0 (2H, s, CH₂ of pyrazolone), 5.3 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.4 (1H, s, NH), 11.6 (1H, s, NH of pyrazolone) ppm (Found : C, 45.9; H, 4.9; N, 22.9. C₇H₉N₃O₃ required : C, 45.8; H, 4.8; N, 22.8%).

The physical and analytical data have been given in Table 1.

6-Methyl-1,3-dihydro-4*H*,7*H*-pyrazolo[2,3-*c*]pyridine-4-one (4) :

Conventional method : A mixture of *N*-(pyrazol-2-ene-5-one-3-yl)-3-oxo-butanamide 3 (0.183 g, 1 mmol) in 7 ml DMF and catalytic amount of HCl refluxed for 10 h in an oil bath. After cooling the reaction mixture, the solid separated out was filtered and washed with ethanol to get the yellow solid.

Microwave method: A mixture of *N*-(pyrazol-2-ene-5-one-3-yl)-3-oxobutanamide **3** (0.183 g, 1 mmol) in 5 ml DMF and catalytic amount of HCl was irradiated in domestic microwave oven for 4 min with intermittent stirring. The reaction mixture is then cooled and separated solid was filtered and washed with ethanol to get yellow solid; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3422 (NH), 1676 (C=O of pyrazolone), 1612 (C=N), 1543 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.28 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.6 (1H, s, CH), 5.41 (1H, d, NH), 5.49 (1H, s, CH), 12.0 (1H, s, NH) ppm (Found : C, 50.9; H, 4.2; N, 25.4. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ required : C, 50.8; H, 4.3; N, 25.2%).

The physical and analytical data have been given in Table 1.

Experimental

Hydrazino ethylcarboxylate (5): The ethylchloroformate (0.108 g, 1 mmol) was added slowly with constant stirring to a solution of hydrazine hydrate (0.048 g, 1 mmol). After complete addition of ethyl chloroformate, a white coloured solid obtained, was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol to get colourless crystals. Yield 85%; m.p. 90 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.25 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.97 (1H, bs, NH), 4.19 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 7.7 (2H, bs, NH_2) ppm.

1-Carboethoxy-5-amino-pyrazol-4-ene-3-one (6): A mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate (0.106 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazino ethyl carboxylate (0.104 g, 1 mmol) was refluxed in 7 ml ethanol for 2 h in an oil bath. On cooling the reaction mixture, separated solid was filtered, to get white crystals. Yield 85%; m.p. 105 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3246–3041 (NHNH_2), 1753 (C=O of ester), 1697 (C=O of pyrazolone ring), 1533, 1482 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.27 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.9 (1H, bs, NH), 4.19 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 6.5 (2H, bs, NH_2), 7.1 (1H, s, =CH) (Found : C, 42.47; H, 6.24; N, 37.15. $\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}$ required : C, 42.3; H, 6.20; N, 37.20%).

Thiourea derivatives of 1-carboethoxy-5-amino-pyrazol-4-ene-3-one (7): A mixture of 1-carboethoxy-5-

amino-pyrazol-4-ene-3-one (0.171 g, 1 mmol), phenylisothiocyanate (0.063 g, 1 mmol) in ethanolic KOH (1 N, 3 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water. The white coloured solid precipitate out was filtered and recrystallized from EtOH to get **7**. Yield 70%; m.p. 127 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3200–3041 (NH), 1753 (C=O of ester), 1697 (C=O of pyrazolone ring), 1533, 1482 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.39 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 4.2 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 4.6 (1H, bs, NH), 7.1 (1H, bs, =CH), 7.1–7.5 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.6 (1H, bs, NH), 10.1 (1H, bs, NHPH) ppm (Found : C, 53.21; H, 4.87; N, 22.56. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$ required : C, 53.3; H, 4.7; N, 22.49%).

Pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]dihydrothiazole (8): The mixture of compound **7** (0.294 g, 1 mmol) in 5 ml ethanol and catalytic amount of gl. AcOH was refluxed for 2 h in an oil bath. On cooling the reaction mixture was poured onto ice-cold water. A white coloured solid separated out was filtered, washed with cold water to yield compound **8**. Yield 67%; m.p. 155 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.41 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 4.2 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 4.6 (1H, bs, NH), 6.9–7.6 (5H, m, Ar-H), 9.6 (1H, bs, NHPH) ppm (Found : C, 53.64; H, 4.09; N, 22.75. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$ required : C, 53.5; H, 4.1; N, 22.6%).

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References

1. C. Hardy, *Adv. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1984, **36**, 343; Japan Kokai, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **84**, 164771; C. Kuosh, L. Huang and H. Nakamura, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1984, **27**, 439; R. Motokuni, M. Tauaka, S. Hashimoto and T. Suzuc, Japan Kokai, 7778895; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, **87**, 168629m; R. Orth, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, **57**, 537 and reference cited therein; M. Elnagdi, M. Elmoghayar and K. Sadek, *Adv. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1990, **48**, 223.
2. A. M. El-Dean, A. A. Aralla, T. A. Mohamed and A. A. Geies, *Z. Naturforsch, Teil B : Chem. Sci.*, 1991, **46**, 541.
3. Y. Fujikama, M. Suzuki, H. Iwasaki, M. Sakashita and M. Kitahara, *Eur. Pat. Appl. EP339*, 1989, **71**, 358.